

VehicLens: An Integrated AI System for Vehicle Classification and Occupant Analysis in Border Security Applications

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ABSTRACT

As border security challenges continue to evolve, the need for effective inspection tools becomes increasingly critical. This paper introduces a novel system, named VehicLens, that integrates a custom-developed vehicle classification module with an integrated facial detection and gender categorization component. Additionally, a dataset created explicitly for training and testing the neural network responsible for the vehicle classification part of VehicLens is presented.

Given that VehicLens is intended to be part of a Border Security Application, significant emphasis was placed on ensuring that the dataset contains realistic data to achieve robust performance under actual operational conditions. Therefore, the dataset comprises images of both new and primarily used vehicles, encompassing various conditions such as damages and modifications, rather than focusing solely on pristine new vehicles captured in ideal scenarios.

Upon successful classification of the vehicle model by the system, the captured image undergoes further analysis via the facial detection and gender categorization parts of the tool. The advanced capabilities of these modules allow the system to predict the number of occupants inside the recognized vehicle, as well as their gender. The multi-modal analysis enables security personnel to identify potential security issues either through prior knowledge about incoming vehicles at border crossings or by identifying discrepancies between system predictions and the lists of pre-registered travelers provided by applications such as the one developed within the scope of the EINSTEIN project (GA.101121280). By working in conjunction with such pre-registration systems, VehicLens allows border guards to access critical information about a vehicle and its occupants prior to its arrival at the checkpoint. This early availability of data grants them additional time for inspection, ultimately enhancing the level of security while also reducing waiting times for travelers.

Keywords: Vehicle Model Classification; Facial Detection; Gender Categorization; Occupant Analysis; Border Security.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent risk assessments conducted by European agencies underscore document fraud as a major challenge in contemporary border management. According to a Frontex report, in 2021 alone, more than 19,000 individuals were detected using approximately 25,000 fraudulent documents at the EU's external borders and during intra-Schengen secondary movements. The same report highlights growing concerns regarding the continual enhancement of forgery techniques, as well as the anticipated rise in identity fraud incidents¹. The rising number of fraudulent documents, combined with their increasing sophistication, clearly demonstrates the need for new multi-modal tools to enable law enforcement agencies to keep pace with evolving threats.

VehicLens is proposed as a tool that can complement existing border security applications (such as the Pre-Registration and Border Control apps developed within the scope of the EINSTEIN project) or operate as a standalone solution. The

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tool processes images captured by border cameras to classify the exact model of the travelers' vehicle. In addition, VehicLens predicts the number of occupants inside the vehicle and classifies their gender. This multi-layered information can provide valuable support to law enforcement officers, particularly when they have a list of expected vehicles and occupants—either generated through pre-registration systems like the one developed in the EINSTEIN project or obtained through internal intelligence about suspect vehicles.

In this work, the methodologies that comprise the proposed tool will be presented. In order for VehicLens to provide the information previously described, it leverages the predictions of three distinct models. One model is responsible for car model classification, another for face detection, and a third for the gender classification of the detected faces. For the training and testing of the first model, a dedicated dataset named Car_Models_300k was also created.

The Car_Models_300k dataset contains more than 300,000 images, as its name suggests. The aim was to create a dataset encompassing a wide range of different car models, both modern and older ones, captured under realistic conditions. To achieve this, images of used vehicles were deliberately selected, ensuring that the dataset includes vehicles exhibiting natural wear and aging effects.

2. RELATED WORK

To the best of our knowledge, there is no other tool that offers multimodal analysis alongside the full range of information provided by the system presented in this work. However, several standalone neural networks have been developed to address individual functionalities of the proposed tool.

Regarding the task of vehicle classification, the most similar approach we identified in terms of design and architecture is the "stanford-car-vit-patch16" model². This model has been published on the Hugging Face platform by the user "therealcyberlord" and is trained on the Stanford Car Dataset³, which comprises 16,185 images equally split between training and testing sets. The images in this dataset have a resolution of 360×240 pixels.

Although it is based on a Vision Transformer architecture (specifically, the google/vit-base-patch16-224 variant⁴) it is a considerably heavier model, with approximately 85.9 million parameters. It is capable of recognizing 196 vehicle categories; however, it lacks several modern as well as some older classes. Despite having fewer categories, its overall accuracy reaches 86%, which is lower than the accuracy achieved by the model presented in this work.

3. METHODOLOGIES

3.1 Dataset

To train and evaluate the VehicLens model responsible for vehicle model classification, a dataset comprising RGB images of various car models was required. Each image needed to be annotated with the corresponding label, that is, the name of the car model depicted.

In order for the model to achieve high accuracy in real-life scenarios, it is crucial that the training images reflect real-world conditions. In this context, the dataset must include car models that are commonly found on the road, spanning both older and more recent models. For this reason, we opted to construct a new dataset rather than rely on publicly available datasets, many of which were outdated and lacked representations of modern vehicles.

Furthermore, it was important that the images portray vehicles in natural, everyday conditions. Images of brand-new, unused cars alone were deemed insufficient, as they fail to reflect wear and tear accumulated over time, such as faded paint or potential damage from collisions, characteristics that are common in vehicles observed in operational environments. These two key considerations led to the decision to construct the dataset through a web scraping process, targeting websites dedicated to the sale of both new and used vehicles. More specifically, the selected website is <https://www.autotrader.co.uk>.

As will be discussed in the following section, the architecture selected for this task is a Vision Transformer, a data-hungry model that typically requires large volumes of training samples to perform effectively. Consequently, it was necessary to develop an RGB dataset that contains a sufficient number of images along with their corresponding labels (i.e., the car

model names depicted). The dataset was designed to be large enough to enable the neural network to learn effectively, while also being constrained in size to ensure that training over multiple epochs would remain computationally feasible within a reasonable timeframe.

The Car_Models_300k dataset ultimately comprises 307,517 images. This number was achieved following an automated duplicate removal process, as many vehicle listings reused the same promotional images sourced from the official websites of car manufacturers. In addition, images depicting the interior of vehicles were excluded, as they were deemed irrelevant for the intended application scenario (namely, border security systems where the VehicLens camera is assumed to be positioned outside the vehicle).

The dataset includes 336 car model categories, a figure that resulted after filtering out certain vehicle types that lacked a sufficient number of images for effective training (e.g., rare or antique cars). To ensure class balance and model robustness, upper and lower bounds were established for the number of training samples per class. Specifically, any category containing fewer than 100 training images was removed entirely from the dataset, while for categories exceeding 1,000 training images, only the excess images were discarded to maintain uniformity.

After these constraints were applied, the final size of the dataset was fixed at 307,517 images. Given the substantial volume of data, the dataset was split into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) subsets. This corresponds to 245,951 images for training, 30,684 for validation, and 30,882 for testing.

3.2 Proposed tool

The core objective of the VehicLens system is to perform multi-modal visual analysis of vehicles and their occupants using photographs captured at border checkpoints. To achieve this, the system employs a pipeline consisting of three distinct deep learning models. The first is a vehicle classification model trained on the Car_Models_300k dataset that was previously presented. In addition, two pretrained models are used, one for face detection and one for gender classification.

3.2.1 Overview of the Pipeline

The VehicLens system takes a single RGB image as input and outputs the predicted vehicle model, the number of occupants, and the gender of each detected individual. The processing pipeline is illustrated in Figure 1.

The output of the vehicle classification model is not required for the subsequent face and gender analysis but is included in the final annotated image. The bounding boxes generated by the face detection model are used to crop the corresponding regions in the original image, and these cropped face images are then passed to the gender classification model for inference.

Figure 1 Flowchart of the VehicLens

3.2.2 Vehicle Model Classification

The neural network selected for the vehicle model classification feature of the tool is based on the MobileViTv3 architecture⁵. MobileViTv3 was chosen due to its excellent balance between classification accuracy and computational efficiency, making it well-suited for potential deployment in resource-constrained environments. This compact Vision Transformer variant integrates lightweight convolutional layers with attention mechanisms, enabling efficient and effective visual representation learning.

Figure 2 MobileViT architecture as shown in the paper⁶

The model was trained with the training set of the Car_Models_300k dataset that was presented in Section 3.1. To improve generalization and prevent the model from becoming overly confident in its predictions, label smoothing was applied during training. This regularization technique allowed the neural network to be trained for a high number of epochs, 600 epochs in particular, with a reduced risk of overfitting. Moreover, for optimization, the AdamW optimizer was employed, which decouples weight decay from the gradient-based update, offering better generalization and improved convergence in comparison to the standard Adam optimizer.

3.2.3 Face Detection

In order for VehicLens to estimate the number of occupants in a vehicle, it was decided to detect only those faces visible through the windows and windshield. To this end, a pre-trained model based on the Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks (MTCNN)⁷ architecture was employed. MTCNN was selected for its robustness in accurately detecting facial regions across a wide range of poses and lighting conditions, which is crucial given the outdoor setting of border checkpoints and the varying times at which images may be captured. The detector is applied to the same input image used for vehicle classification and returns a set of bounding boxes corresponding to the detected faces. Each detected face is then cropped and passed to the subsequent processing stage for further analysis.

3.2.4 Gender Classification

The final stage of the pipeline involves classifying the gender of each detected occupant. For this task, a pre-trained Vision Transformer (ViT) model was employed. Specifically, a model named “gender-classification”, available on the Hugging Face platform and uploaded by the user “rizvandwiki”⁸, was utilized. This model was fine-tuned on gender-labeled facial images and outputs a label, either “male” or “female”, along with a confidence score. The face crops generated by the MTCNN detector are processed individually by the ViT model. The system then overlays the prediction results onto the image using color-coded bounding boxes (e.g., blue for male, red for female) to ensure clear visual representation.

3.2.5 Integration and Output

Upon completion of all three stages, the system compiles the predictions into a single annotated image, which is then saved locally. The output includes the original image with overlaid annotations: the predicted vehicle model and its corresponding confidence score, the total number of detected occupants, and a breakdown of male and female occupants, each marked with color-coded bounding boxes.

Figure 3 Example output image of VehicLens

4. RESULTS

In this section, we present the results of the conducted experiments. The experiments focused on the model responsible for vehicle model classification, as it is the only one among the three models that is not pre-trained and thoroughly tested on the specific task it is designed to perform.

For the evaluation of the model, the test set from the Car_Models_300k dataset was utilized. This set comprises 30,882 images across 336 categories. Although the dataset is unbalanced, no single category contains more than 125 images. The following two tables provide metrics that describe the overall performance of the model.

	Top-1	Top-5
Accuracy	0.8840	0.9533

Table 1 Top-k Accuracy Metrics for Vehicle Classification Model

As shown in the Table 1 the model demonstrates strong performance with 88.40% top-1 accuracy and 95.33% top-5 accuracy . These results indicate that the model not only correctly identifies the exact car model in nearly 9 out of 10 test cases, but also includes the correct model within its top 5 predictions for over 95% of the test samples.⁹

	Precision	Recall	F1 - Score
Macro-averaged	0.8854	0.8741	0.8782
Weighted-averaged	0.8863	0.8840	0.8842

Table 2 Precision, Recall, and F1 Score Metrics for Vehicle Classification Model

The close alignment between macro-averaged (0.8782) and weighted-averaged (0.8842) F1-scores indicates consistent performance across classes, despite variation in class representation (ranging from 13 to 125 samples per class).

Although the confusion matrix with all the classes provides an overall view of the model’s performance, it is difficult to discern specific results due to high number of classes. For this reason, we grouped the vehicle models based on their manufacturer and generated a new confusion matrix. This approach facilitates easier interpretation and additionally provides insight into the model’s effectiveness at the manufacturer level.

Figure 5 Per - class analytics of VehicLens

Although there were a few exceptions, such as the "SsangYong Korando" category mentioned earlier, the per-class F1-score distribution reveals remarkably consistent performance across the 336 classes. Specifically, 296 categories (accounting for 88.1% of the total) achieved an F1 score greater than 0.8. Thirty-eight classes fall within the moderate performance range ($0.50 \leq F1 < 0.80$), while only two categories—including "SsangYong Korando"—exhibit an F1 score below 0.50. Additionally, 19 other classes achieved perfect precision (1.0), albeit with varying recall rates.

5. CONCLUSION

This work introduced VehicLens, a novel AI-powered tool designed for border security applications, which performs multi-modal analysis by combining vehicle model classification with occupant detection and gender categorization. The system leverages three specialized neural networks to extract layered information from images captured at border checkpoints, offering authorities a comprehensive view that includes vehicle identification and insights into the occupants.

A key contribution of this work is the development of the Car_Models_300k dataset, a large-scale collection of over 300,000 images designed specifically to reflect real-world conditions. This dataset contains both images of more modern and recent vehicle models and used vehicles that show signs of wear and aging. The use of this dataset allowed the vehicle classification model, based on the MobileViTV3 architecture, to achieve high accuracy (88.40% top-1, 95.33% top-5), while remaining lightweight and deployable in resource-constrained environments.

The integration of face detection and gender classification further enhances the tool’s utility by providing information about the number and gender of vehicle occupants. This layered information can be instrumental in verifying pre-registration data or identifying anomalies during manual checks, thus enhancing situational awareness and supporting informed decision-making at border control points.

Overall, VehicLens represents a meaningful step forward in augmenting traditional border control systems with AI-driven visual analysis, offering a practical and scalable solution to emerging security challenges.

6. FUTURE WORK

The proposed tool employs three distinct neural networks. One of the primary reasons behind the selection of lightweight model architectures—such as the MobileViTv3 architecture for the vehicle classification task—was to ensure compatibility with hardware platforms that are limited in computational resources. A key objective for future development is to optimize the tool further so that it can be transformed into a mobile application capable of running locally on edge devices or mobile platforms.

In addition, although the current model demonstrates promising overall performance, it was observed that it underperforms in two specific vehicle categories. To address this limitation, we plan to enrich the training set of the Car_Models_300k dataset with additional samples specifically targeting these underrepresented categories. We will then retrain the classification network with the enhanced dataset in order to improve the model’s accuracy in those categories and consequently boost the overall performance. We are currently evaluating the possibility of publishing the Car_Models_300k dataset as an open-access resource, following the inclusion of the aforementioned supplementary images.

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